

Identification of district heating and cooling system archetypes: a novel approach applied to a case study in Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

District Heating and Cooling (DHC) systems are central to the decarbonisation of thermal energy supply. For efficient development and assessment of decarbonisation strategies amongst these diverse systems, it is essential to identify representative system archetypes that can serve as proxies for broader types in targeted case studies. Existing work often focuses on single-criteria and supply-side classifications, while overlooking demand-side diversity and the role of exergy in evaluating system performance. This study introduces a novel multi-criteria methodology for the demand-based characterisation and grouping of DHC districts, with exergy as a central metric. The method proposes four criteria to characterise supply regions on GIS-based data: exergy demand density (in place of traditional energy demand), degree of connection to reflect densification potential, and two building stock indicators reflecting ownership patterns and usage types to incorporate a social dimension. The methodology applies a K-medoids algorithm to group similar systems and identify representative archetypes within each group. To demonstrate the approach, it was applied to publicly available data on existing Swiss DHC systems. As the required data on supply regions was not readily available, it was first generated through a GIS-based analysis, using DBSCAN clustering to define district boundaries based on building-level information. This enabled the application of the proposed criteria and the identification of five distinct archetypes for Swiss DHC systems. Due to the slightly delayed perspective of the Swiss dataset, recent developments such as low-temperature networks are underrepresented while capturing the more established, higher-temperature networks where decarbonisation needs remain particularly significant.

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability, understanding the dynamics and characteristics of district heating and cooling (DHC) systems has become crucial. DHC systems play a significant role in the efficient and fossil-free distribution and management of thermal energy. Despite their importance, comprehensive methodologies for systematically identifying and categorising these systems remain limited. A meaningful classification must include not only technical supply-side aspects but also non-technical - especially demand-side - characteristics, as demand forms the basis for evaluating supply structures. While extensive efforts have been made to identify and categorise buildings according to various attributes, similar systematic approaches for DHC systems are sparse. In this paper, the term DHC systems is used generically, although in many specific cases it refers to pure heating

applications.

DHC systems are generally described by a broad range of technical attributes. Books and guidelines like those proposed by Nussbaumer et al. [1], Rutz et al. [2] or Oppermann et al. [3] give a good overview on technical and economical properties of the network infrastructure. Hangartner et al. [4], Sulzer et al. [5] and Werner [6] clearly define a vocabulary that addresses relevant technical attributes. Frederiksen and Werner in Ref. [7] and Lund et al. in Ref. [8] introduced the concept of network generations, which has been broadly adopted by the scientific community. Generational classification represents the continuous reduction of network temperatures along with increasing efficiencies and shares of renewables, ranging from early high temperature steam networks (1st generation) to low and ultra-low temperature networks in later 4th and 5th generations. Network temperature is perhaps the most relevant attribute to distinguish between network generations. A similar

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Fig. 1. Basic distinction of DHC system characteristics into demand and supply side. From their perspective, archetypal districts and archetypal networks can be identified, which interact with each other and define the archetypes of DHC systems as combinations of the two sides.

approach, more focused on low temperature networks (i.e. operating below 60 °C) was introduced by Hangartner et al. [4]. The proposed classification distinguishes networks based on four temperature levels, which determine their applicability for space heating, cooling, and domestic hot water production. Apart from network temperature, networks are often distinguished by size as proposed by Rutz et al. [2] or by energy source as suggested by Persson and Werner [9]. Triebes et al. [10] developed a data-based multi-criteria classification on CHP-fired networks in Germany. Data of 140 DHC systems was collected and an agglomerative clustering with 4 dimensionless key figures, focusing on different technical characteristics of the CHP units, was used to identify 8 types of systems. Werner [6] analysed an inventory of 165 implemented, planned, or proposed cases of 4th generation networks and buildings from 19 countries, resulting in 6 main groups of system configurations. Those classifications and configurations are focused on technical supply properties of DHC systems. Nevertheless, demand properties are essential to define pathways for the decarbonisation of districts. Exergy will play a central role in the characterisation of demand, since it offers a more accurate measure to assess the relevant efficiency (exergetic instead of energetic) of DHC systems and reveal potentials not visible by energy-based views alone, as correctly concluded by Kotlanien et al. [11]. This metric has increasingly been used to assess the efficiency of DHC systems, particularly in case studies such as those by Li et al. [12] and Veyron et al. [13], but also in more general works like Gong & Werner in Ref. [14] or Topal et al. in Ref. [15].

Given the heterogeneity of demand structures, a reduction in complexity is needed to generalise insights. GIS-based approaches are widely used in DHC research for automated layout design and optimisation, as shown by Tzouganakis et al. [16] and Chicherin [17]. Vrain et al. [18] apply spatially explicit methods for scenario development. A key input for such studies is the location and characteristics of existing DHC systems, as compiled by Pelda et al. [19] in a district heating atlas for Germany. However, these datasets mainly focus on technical aspects such as energy use, pipe length, and temperatures, often overlooking demand-side features. On a more high-level perspective, Munčán et al. [20] contributed a literature-based assessment that, beyond technical aspects, also considers economic and regulatory frameworks across European countries.

In building energy modelling (BEM), the use of building archetypes is a well-established strategy for reducing complexity. The study of building archetypes aims to identify representative models that capture the common characteristics of buildings within a specific context using various approaches [21]. This context could be defined by factors like building type, climate zone, construction period or energy performance and the approaches strongly depend on the availability of information and the field of interest. The systematic identification of archetypes within BEM using clustering techniques has proven effective in

simplifying complex energy systems, enabling targeted interventions [22] and allowing comparison of results using the same basis. For instance, Alrasheed & Moushed [23] emphasises the role of archetype classification using the k-prototype clustering method to improve energy performance simulations. Similarly, Dahlström et al. [24] discuss the benefits of a novel multi-parameter cluster analysis approach for identifying representative building archetypes within the Swedish residential building stock.

Inspired by BEM methodologies, this study introduces a novel, archetype-based approach to identify and characterise representative DHC systems. Rather than attempting to optimise individual DHC systems in isolation, the archetype approach enables the identification of a manageable set of representative systems that approximate the diversity of system configurations in the most effective way. The methodology presented is applied to the case study of Switzerland to identify a suitable number of Swiss DHC system archetypes. Importantly, the methodology itself is region-independent and can be applied to any regional/supra regional context.

This study does not provide system-level optimisation or regulatory guidance. Instead, it enables identification of DHC archetypes through a comprehensive, demand-oriented, and not purely technical lens. These archetypes offer a foundation for technical, economic, and regulatory analysis, allowing findings to be projected onto the wider heating and cooling sector. This enhances understanding and supports more effective design, planning, and policymaking.

2. Methodology

DHC systems exhibit a range of characteristics that can be analysed from technical, economic, and social perspectives. This study distinguishes systems based on two property groups: supply infrastructure and district characteristics. With the perspective of these characteristics, archetypal networks and archetypal districts can be identified, which in combination define an archetype of DHC systems as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Supply-side properties include generation capacity, energy sources, and network infrastructure – typically tied to technical and economic factors. Demand characteristics however, concern consumption behaviour, exergy requirements and the profiles of different building types within the district, which also reflect social characteristics. Most studies focus on supply-side aspects or individual networks, often overlooking comparative or socio-economic insights. Thus, our research pivots towards a demand-side perspective, recognising that supply systems exist to meet demand efficiently. Consequently, the structure and characteristics of the energy demand are crucial for a meaningful comparison of DHC systems. By examining the demand-side, we acknowledge that the efficiency of the network should be measured by its ability to meet the energy requirements of the connected buildings effectively and sustainably, and that the successful implementation of DHC systems depends on more than just technical aspects.

The novelty of this work lies not in any single new metric, but in the integration of multiple underused perspectives into one framework.

- A demand-oriented lens that includes technical and social dimensions (e.g. building type and use as proxies for ownership).
- Use of exergy demand density instead of traditional energy demand density.

While these aspects exist individually in literature, their combined application in a comparative, multi-district framework represents a new methodological contribution. Exergy analysis is common in HVAC but applying exergy demand density to define DHC supply areas remains rare.

2.1. Description of districts

A method is proposed that identifies the buildings connected to the

Fig. 2. Example of 100 m × 100 m raster field to capture the supply area of a network as a polygon. Red dots indicate buildings connected to the network; yellow dots the non-connected buildings within the polygon; grey dots the non-connected buildings outside the polygon.

Fig. 3. Heat transfer station with the flow and return temperatures on both the primary and secondary side of the system.

Table 1

Definition of flow and return temperatures depending on building age and assumed heat transmission system. Old radiators require the highest flow temperatures. Floor heating has a lower temperature difference between flow and return.

Construction Period	Heat transmission system	Flow temperature	Return temperature
≤1970	Radiator	70 °C 343 K	55 °C 328 K
1971–1990	Radiator	60 °C 333 K	45 °C 318 K
1991–2005	Radiator	50 °C 323 K	35 °C 308 K
≥2005	Floor heating	35 °C 308 K	25 °C 298 K

DHC networks, delineates the served areas, and describes districts based on building characteristics. First, district area must be spatially defined. Knowing the buildings connected to a DHC network, the area is

Fig. 4. Arbitrary example of a point cloud in a 2-dimensional space and three groups/medoids to be identified. Colour indicates affiliation to group A, B, or C, and the filled circles mark the points that form the medoid for each group. The algorithm minimizes the sum of all distances between all points within each group and their corresponding medoids.

delineated by drawing a polygon around the building cluster using a defined distance and method. We propose using contiguous 100 m × 100 m geo raster cells, as shown in Fig. 2. This is inspired by the common use of hectare grid cells in Switzerland for area-based analyses, such as waste heat potential and heat demand mapping by Chambers et al. [25] and Schneider et al. [26]. Cells are centred on the cluster, and only those containing at least one connected building are included. Within this polygon, both connected and non-connected buildings are considered.

For each building, the exergy demands are estimated based on location, building type, age and size. Further insights are provided in chapter 2.2. Based on this demand data and additional building information, four key performance indicators (KPI) are derived for each cluster: (1) The degree of connection (DOC) weighted by exergy demand, quantifying the share of demand that is currently supplied by the network and indicates the potential for enhancing network connectivity within the area; (2) exergy demand density, defined as the total exergy demand per unit area, a novel metric proposed to replace the traditional energy density indicator thereby offering a more precise measure to incorporate resource efficiency considerations; (3) share of residential energy reference area (ERA), indicating variation in user profiles; (4) share of single-family houses amongst residential buildings, offering insights into ownership patterns. Exergy demand constitutes a central part of KPIs (1) and (2) and the estimation methodology is described below.

2.2. Exergy demand estimation

As stated by Gong & Werner in Ref. [27], exergetic efficiency was less relevant during the era of fossil-fuelled heating systems. For future systems relying on renewables and waste heat, using high-quality sources (e.g. gas, biomass) to produce low-quality heat for building application is inefficient. Thus, evaluating networks by their exergetic performance is essential for cost-effective energy transitions. While the exergy approach remains rarer in literature than energetic approaches, some literature deals extensively with an exergetic view on thermal

Fig. 5. Network count by main energy source [36]. Biomass includes logs, wood chips, pellets, and biogas. Location-bound low-temperature sources include lake and river water, groundwater, wastewater, and shallow geothermal. Fossil sources include heating oil, natural gas, and natural gas cogeneration plant. Other waste heat includes waste heat from nuclear power plant and tunnel waste heat. Data from SFOE [36], June 2023.

Fig. 6. DHC system power distribution by main energy source. Air + HP has a 0.002 % value and solar thermal 0 % (not shown). Data from SFOE [36], June 2023.

networks. Gong & Werner [27] calculate exergy demand E by heat demand Q multiplied by an exergy factor ϵ : $E = Q \cdot \epsilon$

If unknown, heat demand must be estimated based on building properties and location. The basic principle consists of estimating the

annual area specific space heating and hot water demand of a building based on type, age and location. This value must then be multiplied by given or estimated building energy reference area (ERA). For Swiss residential and service building stock, ERA is evaluated using the

Fig. 7. Part of the city of Basel with polygons drawn in QGIS. Red dots indicate buildings connected to a network and coloured areas mark the supply areas of different networks [42]. Dots within polygons form the building cluster supplied by the corresponding DHC network.

methodology of Schluck et al. [28], area specific heat demand on values from Streicher et al. [29] and the Swiss norm SIA 2024 [30].

As the space heating and hot water demands have different temperature requirements, exergy demand is calculated separately using different exergy factors. A range of formulas for exergy factor ε of network-based heat supply have been presented in literature, each with their individual particularities. For a heat flow transferred from/to a fluid that changes the fluid temperature from T_1 to T_2 with reference temperature T_{ref} , the exergy factor is defined as follows [27]:

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_1 - T_2} \ln\left(\frac{T_1}{T_2}\right) \quad (i)$$

To apply this formula, three key aspects have to be defined first.

a) Reference environment

Most prominently, there is the question how to define the reference environment, which in this case reduces to the reference temperature. In IEA Annex 49 by Torío & Schmidt [31] four options are examined: he universe (≈ 0 K), indoor air, undisturbed ground, and ambient air. They recommend using outdoor air as the reference environment for exergy analysis in building energy systems.

b) Time-dependency

Outdoor temperature fluctuates daily, seasonally, and geographically, making the choice of reference temperature complex. Pons [32] argues that reference temperatures should be chosen constant, while Torío & Schmidt distinguish between steady-state and dynamic

approaches [31]. Dynamic approaches consider fluctuating reference temperatures accompanied by fluctuating exergy content, thus capturing storage effects. However, this requires dynamic modelling. Steady-state approaches use average system and outdoor temperatures over a defined period. Torío & Schmidt [33] applied this using local average outdoor temperature during the heating season. Gong & Werner [27] used the yearly average temperature of central northern Europe. This approach is based on both temporal and spatial averaging. In Ref. [31], monthly local averages for the coldest and warmest months were used. The authors concluded that steady-state exergy analysis provides correct insights during exergy performance assessment and is suitable for system comparison.

c) Choice of system boundaries

As stated by Stephan & Schebek in Ref. [34], “energy and exergy losses are either included or omitted in the results” depending on system boundary selection. Key considerations include.

- Demand side: Either the temperature of useful heat is chosen, i.e. room temperature for space heating and tap temperature for domestic hot water. This captures exergy destruction in the distribution system and is suitable for full supply chain analysis. Alternatively, water temperatures on primary or secondary side at the heat transfer station can be used when changes in the building distribution system are not considered.
- Supply side: The boundary can either include the energy conversion unit or focus solely on the water temperatures within the flow and

Fig. 8. Process to identify Swiss District Heating and Cooling (DHC) systems. The Register of Buildings and Dwellings (RBD) database contains information on buildings connected to DHC networks. The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) database contains information on thermal networks including their location. Depending on the geospatial relations amongst the DHC systems, buildings and networks were clustered and linked either manually or automatically.

return pipes, depending on whether conversion efficiency is of interest.

The approach of Torio & Schmidt [33] was chosen, using local average outdoor temperature during the heating season from October to April for each system. This is consistent with their recommendation in Ref. [31]. The system boundary to quantify exergy demand is drawn to include the water temperatures on the secondary side (Fig. 3).

It is assumed that existing building heat distribution systems remain unchanged, keeping temperature demand constant. Exergy loss at the heat transfer station is still considered and decreases with lower primary supply temperatures. The analysis is restricted to the residential and service sector and therefore consists of space heating and domestic hot water demands, excluding process heat.

The exergy factor for space heat supply ε_{SH} is calculated using the

flow and return temperatures T_F and T_R of the secondary side according to Ref. [27]:

$$\varepsilon_{SH} = 1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_F - T_R} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{T_F}{T_R}\right) \quad (ii)$$

For each individual building, the flow and return temperatures are estimated based on age according to Table 1.

For domestic hot water production, the exergy factor ε_{DHW} is the same but replaces flow temperature with the target hot water temperature of $T_{DHW} = 60^\circ\text{C}$ (333 K), stipulated to prevent Legionella growth, and the return temperature with an approximate freshwater temperature of $T_{FW} = 10^\circ\text{C}$ (283 K):

$$\varepsilon_{DHW} = 1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_{DHW} - T_{FW}} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{T_{DHW}}{T_{FW}}\right) \quad (iii)$$

Fig. 9. Several automatically identified DHC systems. The markers represent network coordinates, which usually correspond to the position of the energy conversion units (taken from the SFOE list); points represent the location of buildings connected to networks (taken from the RBD). Black points represent outliers. Markers and points with the same colour represent a DHC system.

2.3. Grouping of DHC systems

The previous sections describe the methodology of characterising districts using the following four KPIs as introduced in section 2.1.

- (1) Degree of connection (DOC) weighted by exergy demand
- (2) Exergy demand density
- (3) Share of residential energy reference area (ERA)
- (4) Share of single-family houses amongst residential buildings

The final step of the methodology consists of grouping similar DHC systems with reference to these KPIs. Inspired by Murray et al. [35] a K-medoid algorithm is used to form groups and identify representative medoids for a set of DHC systems - be it the entire set of all systems or specific subsets. The terms “groups/grouping” are used here to distinguish it from the geospatial “clusters/clustering” of buildings in the following chapter. Unlike geospatial *clustering* in *real-world* 2D coordinates, *grouping* takes place in a *n-dimensional KPI space*. The algorithm minimizes dissimilarity within each group relative to its *medoid*, a centrally located point. Fig. 4 illustrates this with an arbitrary 2D example with three groups. The selection of KPIs and number of groups is user-defined and tailored to the dataset.

This study uses a 4-dimensional, with each KPI as a dimension and

each point representing a DHC system. Groups contain systems with similar KPI profiles, and the medoid represents the most typical system used as a proxy archetype. To ensure uniform weighting, all metrics are equally normalised. Since KPIs (1), (3) and (4) are percentages, exergy demand density (2) is scaled similarly by normalising it to its maximum variation in the dataset.

This methodology is adaptable to any set of DHC systems, and the set can be curated based on the selected boundary conditions such as region or system size.

3. Case study Switzerland

3.1. Energy supply by district heating and cooling networks in Switzerland

Switzerland has over 1100 registered DHC systems published in a continuously-updated database of the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) [36]. The figures presented from this database are for June 2023. Fig. 5 illustrates network distribution by energy source, revealing that approximately 70 % are biomass-fired. In contrast, Fig. 6 shows distribution by heat supply, indicating that more than 40 % of total heat is provided by Waste-to-Energy (WtE) plants. This disparity highlights the dominance of biomass-fired networks in terms of numbers, and the significant contribution of WtE plants in terms of supply.

Table 2

Nine types of spatial relationships amongst clusters, networks, outliers. According to type, different linking strategies are employed to correctly identify DHC systems. Markers represent network location (from SFOE), and points indicate the location of network-connected buildings (from RBD). All markers are blue before linking, and match building colour afterwards, whereby shared colours represent identified DHC systems. The number of identified systems of each type is given, alongside the percentage of all network-connected buildings these systems represent.

Type	Example before linking	Nr. of clusters	Nr. of networks	Description of local geospatial relations	Required measures for correct identification of individual DHC systems	Example after linking	Nr. of DHC systems	Nr. (%) of buildings
I		93	36'651 (47.6%)					
II		408	13'686 (17.8%)					
III		98	6'875 (8.9%)					
IV		51	2'229 (2.9%)					
V		11	1'376 (1.8%)					
VI		227	600 (0.8%)					
VII		1	0	A cluster does not have a network coordinate nearby	No network to be linked. The cluster forms a DHC system without network information	-	581	7'408 (9.6%)
VIII		0	1	The thermal network does not have clusters/ outliers nearby	The network is excluded for the analysis.	-	0	-
IX		0	0	Outliers with no clusters/ networks nearby	The buildings are excluded for the analysis.	-	0	8'114 (10.5%)

Table 3

Resulting Medoid DHC systems for the four subgroups distinguished by power range and the energy sources biomass and WtE (Waste-to-Energy). Shaded columns give the KPI values for each Medoid. The other columns provide additional information on the five medoids and the group metrics, including number of systems within the groups, connected buildings, as well as total energy and exergy demand.

Source	Power	District/ Location	Medoid Information						Group Information			
			Nr. of Buildings	Power [MW]	Exergy Demand Density [kWh/m ² a]	Degree of Connection [%]	Share of residential ERA [%]	Share of SFH [%]	Nr. of DHC systems	Nr. of Buildings	Energy Demand [GWh/a]	Exergy Demand [GWh/a]
Biomass	<1 MW	Wila ZH	31	0.5	3.4	37	83	79	150	4541	172	23
	1–10 MW	Losone TI	56	7.6	3.0	34	78	67	121	7536	292	38
	>10 MW	Murten FR Pratteln BL	113 346	8.0 15	5.2 5.6	31 54	66 70	55 55	80 19	3949 5170	292 358	40 48
WtE		Renegia LU	628	46	5.5	52	66	50	28	26'285	2340	323

Fig. 10. Topology of the first DHC system archetype, automatically identified via algorithm, located in Wila ZH.

Conventionally, networks utilise fossil fuels for peak load coverage. Biomass-fired networks are of particular interest due to their reliance on a flexible, exergetically valuable, and limited renewable resource. However, Switzerland's biomass potential is limited and already largely utilised [37,38] and should be prioritised for replacing fossil fuels in high-temperature industrial processes. Waste incinerators supplying buildings suffer from low annual and exergetic efficiency, due to unused summer heat and low temperature demands.

3.2. Data availability in Switzerland

The Federal Register of Buildings and Dwellings (RBD) from the Federal Statistical Office provides comprehensive data on Swiss building stock [39] including heating system details to identify DHC-connected buildings. It also includes building type, footprint, and age, useful for estimating usage and energy demand. While cantons manage the database, local communities collect the data, leading to variations in quality and completeness [40].

The aforementioned published list of DHC systems [36] includes network location, energy sources, power, and energy supply. While

Fig. 11. Point cloud of the first subgroup of biomass-fired DHC systems with less than 1 MW power, represented in the six perspectives of the 4D-space. Red crosses indicate the system of Wila.

energy sources are fully documented, other metrics such as power and energy supply are incomplete. As of June 2023, 1194 systems are recorded.

3.3. Identification of swiss DHC systems

Determining the geospatial boundaries of DHC systems involves several steps (see Fig. 8). Buildings connected to thermal networks were selected from the RBD. These form geospatial clusters that need to be identified. Moreover, each cluster requires linkage to its corresponding SFOE listed network wherever possible. Network location is registered by a single coordinate — typically the energy conversion unit's location.

Generally, spatial clustering algorithms identify conglomerations of buildings in close proximity. However, such methods may provide misleading results by wrongly merging adjacent systems in dense urban areas or failing to detect non-contiguous supply areas of large networks.

To address this, buildings in urban areas and supply regions of large networks were manually linked. The program QGIS (Version 3.38.0 [41]) was used to delimit the supply areas of networks based on public municipal and utility data. Intersecting these mapped areas with connected buildings defined the final clusters. Fig. 7 shows an exemplary case illustrating the procedure.

The remaining buildings were clustered using the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise algorithm (DBSCAN) [43], which clusters densely packed points based on a user-defined density criterion. Points not fulfilling the criterion are marked as outliers. A *cluster* is a conglomeration of buildings, and outliers are individual buildings not belonging to a cluster. The threshold was set to at least 5 buildings within a radius of 200 m. Since DBSCAN ignores

network locations, it can mistakenly split a network into multiple clusters or misclassify nearby buildings as outliers.

To refine this, distances among clusters, networks, and outliers were analysed. 9 types of spatial relationships were derived and are described below. Ultimately, the analysis automatically linked clusters, networks and outliers, which define the DHC system. Fig. 9 shows an example with several of such systems.

3.3.1. Spatial relationships

Table 2 describes 9 types of spatial relationships amongst clusters, networks and outliers, as well as corresponding measures that allow correct DHC system identification. Each type is presented with a real-world example of local geospatial relations, the current number of clusters and networks subject to that type of relationship, how buildings would be linked to refine the clustering, the percentage of connected buildings clustered this way, and the number of SFOE-listed DHC systems existing within this type.

Type I is manual clustering and linking of buildings, corresponding to urban agglomerations and large networks as described previously. There were 93 DHC systems of this type that represent almost half of all connected buildings analysed.

All other types correspond to automatic clustering and linking, with consideration to distance amongst clusters, networks and outliers. A maximum distance was defined per cluster, depending on the number of buildings within the cluster, enabling linking between clusters, networks and outliers. Essentially, this distance determined whether sufficient proximity between objects existed and it could be assumed that they belonged together.

Type II represents the ideal situation where a lone cluster identified

Fig. 12. Topology of the second DHC system archetype, automatically identified via algorithm, located in Losone TI. The dots representing the connected buildings are fairly widespread, which results in the low degree of connection (34 %).

Fig. 13. Topology of the archetypal DHC system, automatically identified via algorithm, located in the town of Murten FR.

Fig. 14. Point cloud of the second subgroup of biomass-fired DHC systems with 1–10 MW power represented in the six perspectives of the 4D-space. The dots of the two groups of identified DHC systems are distinguished by colour. Red crosses indicate the systems of Losone and Murten.

Fig. 15. Topology of the archetypal DHC system located in Pratteln. It was created by merging five originally separate networks. The system manually identified using QGIS.

Fig. 16. Point cloud of the third subgroup of biomass-fired DHC systems with more than 10 MW power represented in the six perspectives of the 4D-space. Red cross indicates the Pratteln system.

by DBSCAN is close to only a single network coordinate. In such cases, it is almost certain that in reality all buildings and the network itself belong to the same DHC system. The cluster and network (including potential outliers nearby) were therefore automatically linked. 408 DHC systems were of this type, representing almost 18 % of all connected buildings.

Type III describes when multiple clusters are adjacent to a shared network coordinate and hence most certainly belong together. The clusters and the network (and potential outliers nearby) were automatically linked. 98 DHC systems were of this type, representing approximately 9 % of all connected buildings.

Type IV and V represent situations where multiple networks are close to the same cluster(s). Normally Type I, there was insufficient information to clearly distinguish and link the systems. Hence, cluster(s) and networks (and potential outliers nearby) were automatically linked, resulting in DHC systems with multiple sources. 62 systems were of this type, representing around 5 % of all connected buildings.

Type VI corresponds to the situation where outlier buildings are close to the same network coordinate. Both outlier and network were automatically linked. 227 DHC systems were of this type, representing less than 1 % of all connected buildings.

Type VII describes isolated clusters without a neighbouring network coordinate. These cases are either due to incorrect RBD data or are DHC systems unlisted by SFOE. Such clusters were considered simply as DHC systems without network information. 581 systems were of this type, representing around 10 % of all connected buildings.

Type VIII concerns network coordinates without clusters or outliers nearby. There were 177 such networks which were excluded from further analysis.

Finally, type IX concerns outliers without clusters or networks nearby and were also excluded from further analysis. 10.5 % of the total connected buildings were of this type.

In total, 1469 DHC systems were identified.

3.4. Description and grouping

Starting with the identified systems, districts were described (see Section 2). Only districts with 10 or more buildings were considered (792 districts). Data availability limited the analysis to districts with high-temperature networks that source heat from biomass or WtE-plants. Biomass-fired networks dominate in terms of number and WtE networks are relevant in terms of energy supplied and individual system size. Moreover, focusing on high-temperature systems is thermodynamically justified, as they offer greater potential for improving exergy efficiency. This focus is tailored to Swiss context, although the methodology is universally applicable. Low-temperature are also statistically relevant, but many are new or under construction and not yet recorded in the RBD, disqualifying them for this analysis.

Biomass-fired networks were further subdivided by nominal power, serving as an indicator of size. Where power rating was not directly available, nominal power was estimated by dividing assumed annual heat demand by 2000 full load hours. Three subgroups were defined: small (<1 MW), medium (1–10 MW), and large networks (>10 MW).

K-medoid grouping was applied to each subset in the 4D KPI space, where the term "grouping" distinguishes it from geospatial "clustering" used to identify districts. Here, one to two medoids were searched per subgroup. All metrics were scaled from 0 to 100 % for equal weighting. Since exergy demand density did not inherently fit this scale, it was

Fig. 17. Topology of the WtE plant DHC system archetype, fed by the WtE plant Renergia. It covers districts in the urban agglomeration of the city of Lucerne and the cantonal hospital.

normalised using the 5th and 95th percentiles to avoid distortion by outliers.

4. Results for Switzerland

Table 3 presents the resulting DHC system archetypes (medoids) for each subgroup, detailing KPI values and providing additional metrics for all groups represented by the archetypes. A brief description of each archetype is provided in the following section. Due to the high number and diversity within the subgroup of biomass-fired networks between 1 and 10 MW, it was decided to identify two medoids for this subgroup. Therefore, the four subgroups result in five medoids.

The first archetype is located in the rural village Wila in canton Zurich having a population of just over 2'000 and around 650 buildings, of which 31 are network connected. 90 % of all buildings are residential, with nearly 80 % being single-family houses (SFH). Compared to the other archetypes, energy demand density of the supply area and therefore exergy demand density are low. The network is owned by a cooperative and uses wood chips as the main energy source. Fig. 10 shows the system topology. This archetype represents 150 DHC systems, each connecting on average 30 buildings. The point cloud of these systems in 4D space is shown by the six subplots in Fig. 11.

Losone is a suburban community near Locarno, Ticino, with almost 7'000 inhabitants and 2'000 buildings of which more than 50 % are SFH. Around 80 buildings are for commercial and industrial use, while the rest include multi-family housing (MFH), municipal, and public buildings. Fig. 12 shows the system topology. The network uses wood chips as main energy source and has an oil burner for covering peak loads. Around the central unit indicated by the marker, consumers with high heat demand like schools and commercial buildings are located. This archetype represents 121 DHC systems.

The municipality of Murten consists of a town with a historic centre surrounded by suburban and rural areas and has a population of around 10'000. The network is fed by wood chip boilers and a backup gas

burner. It connects to industrial and commercial buildings around the central heating station and to residential buildings around and within the Old Town. In total 113 buildings are connected. The exergy demand density of 5.2 kWh/m² in the supply area is significantly higher than that of 3.0 kWh/m² in Losone, as the town centre is densely built with historic buildings, and the system connects a lower share of SFH overall. Fig. 13 shows the topology of this archetypal system. This archetype represents 80 DHC systems.

Fig. 14 shows the point cloud for biomass-fired DHC systems between 1 and 10 MW of power, plotted under the six perspectives of the 4D space. In all six perspectives, the two clouds are visually distinguishable to varying degrees. Most overlap exists in the top left plot, where the cloud extends over a much smaller range of values which reduces the weight of those distances within the cloud than in the planes with larger scatter. The share of SFH and the normalised exergy demand density appear to be more significant in this respect, which manifests itself in a clearer separation of the two clouds in the respective subplots of Fig. 14.

Pratteln is an industrial suburb of Basel on the banks of the Rhine with around 15'000 inhabitants. The system covers large parts of the municipality and supplies parts of the industrial area. It was created by merging five originally separate networks that were built and operated by the same cooperative. System topology is shown in Fig. 15. Network heat comes mainly from the combustion of wood chips, with a large proportion being generated by combined heat and power production. A minor proportion comes from sludge incineration at the nearby wastewater treatment plant, and oil burners are currently still used to cover peak loads. The district has a comparably high exergy demand density. The subgroup of biomass fired DHC systems with more than 10 MW power is the smallest with only 19 members and is represented in the six plots of Fig. 16.

Renergia is the municipal WtE plant of central Switzerland located in Perlen. It serves districts in multiple municipalities within the agglomerated region of the city of Lucerne and the cantonal hospital of Lucerne.

Fig. 18. Point cloud of the fourth subgroup of DHC systems fed by WtE plants represented in the six perspectives of the 4D-space. Red crosses indicate the system fed by Renergia.

The district has a high exergy demand density and degree of connection as compared to the other archetypes, and its network is divided into four main branches that are being continuously expanded. These supply districts directly or via sub-networks operating at lower temperatures. One branch feeds two sub-networks with auxiliary fossil burners for peak loads and includes minor waste heat from a local steel plant. Fig. 17 shows the system topology. The system is operated by publicly owned actors. All DHC systems served by the 28 Swiss WtE plants belong to this archetype and are plotted in Fig. 18.

5. Conclusion

In this study, a novel methodology to identify archetypes of District Heating and Cooling (DHC) systems is introduced. The methodology is based on the multi-criteria characterisation of districts, with a strong focus on demand-side properties and the explicit integration of exergy demand. It enables the grouping of districts with similar characteristics and the selection of representative archetypes using a K-medoids clustering algorithm.

In contrast to conventional supply-focused analysis, the proposed method enables the selection of more targeted and representative case studies by accounting for spatial, regulatory, and socio-economic factors embedded in demand structures - factors that significantly influence the feasibility and success of decarbonisation measures. This demand-oriented approach enables its application in both districts with and without existing thermal networks and creates a basis for efficient, demand-based decarbonisation planning. By incorporating exergy, a key parameter is provided that reflects the quality of energy, which aligns with the quality of resources. This enables a more precise evaluation of

efficiency than that provided by pure energy-based measures, as it allows for a comparison of qualities and thus a more accurate assessment of resource utilisation. The methodology in its core supplies a flexible framework for defining variable analysis on the clustering and grouping of GIS information at any scale. Applications in other disciplines such as logistics or spatial planning are possible.

To apply this methodology, a case study was conducted using data on existing DHC systems in Switzerland. As the required spatially defined district data was not readily available, a GIS-based pre-processing step was implemented. This involved the use of the DBSCAN clustering algorithm to delineate district boundaries from building-level data. Additional manual selections were made to account for cases where networks extended over large distances or where multiple systems overlapped. These processing steps generated the input dataset required to perform the archetype identification based on the proposed methodology. A set of 792 systems with sufficient data quality could be identified. Out of this set, the K-Medoid algorithm was used to select 5 systems that serve as representative archetypes. These archetypes reflect distinct combinations of demand density, building use, and densification potential, and serve as simplified yet meaningful representations of the diversity present across the Swiss DHC landscape. The results highlight the importance of spatial and qualitative data to carry out a comprehensive analysis, as can be seen by the fact that only around 800 DHC systems of the more than 1100 systems provided sufficient information to be considered in the analysis. In particular, the data basis lags behind the actual development, which means that systems with low-temperature sources, which have seen strong growth in the recent past, are underrepresented in the data and were therefore not taken into account. The presented archetypes are thus restricted to systems

with high-temperature sources. However, this is concomitant with the fact that these systems with their high-exergy sources have the greater potential in terms of increasing exergetic efficiency in the heat supply.

The introduction of these archetypes enables more systematic analyses, analogous to the established building archetypes, by using standardised, representative boundary conditions. This approach avoids the limitations of analysing individual DHC systems in isolation, allowing for broader applicability and comparability of results across different studies. Additionally, the use of archetypes facilitates the identification of suitable decarbonisation pathways for specific types of networks that share similar archetype characteristics, thereby enabling the development of generic guidelines that outline recommended measures and pathways for achieving full decarbonisation of existing DHC systems.

Despite the strengths of the approach, the qualitative tuning of clustering parameters introduces a level of subjectivity, and the sensitivity of results to input data quality suggests a need for further standardisation and validation, particularly across different national contexts. In future work, the method could be applied to updated datasets that better represent emerging low-temperature systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luca Brauchli: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Núria Duran Adroher:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Willy Villasmil:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Markus Auer:** Methodology. **Edward Lucas:** Writing – review & editing. **Philipp Schuetz:** Software, Data curation. **Jörg Worlitschek:** Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and DeepL to generate, translate and linguistically revise text. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Glossary

BEM	Building Energy Modeling
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DHC	District Heating and Cooling
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DOC	Degree Of Connection

ERA	Energy Reference Area
MFH	Multy Family Home
RBD	Register of Buildings and Dwellings
SFH	Single Family Home
SFOE	Swiss Federal Office of Energy
WtE	Waste-to-Energy

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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